

STUDIES ON OPTICAL ACTIVITY AND CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART V. ROTATORY POWERS OF CAMPHORANILIC ACIDS, α - AND β -NAPHTHYLCAMPHORAMIC ACID AT VARIOUS DEGREES OF NEUTRALISATION.

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The rotatory powers of camphoranilic acid, 2', 3', 4'-methylcamphoranilic acids and α - and β -naphthylcamphoramidic acids have been determined at various degrees of neutralisation. In every case the alkali salts have greater rotatory power than the acid. In some cases there is a sudden fall at the half neutralisation point and then a progressive increase till the complete neutralisation point. In other cases, after a gradual increase the rotatory powers become constant and then increase till the acid is completely neutralised.

It is well known that the rotations of acids and bases often diminish in magnitude or become reversed in sign when they are converted into their compounds capable of remaining in an ionised state. α -Phenylpropylacetic acid (Pickard and Yates, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 101) has a rotatory power $[M]_D = +140.7^\circ$ in benzene but its sodium salt has $[M]_D = +5.0^\circ$ in aqueous solution. The sodium salts of lactic and glyceric acids also suffer a similar reversal of sign.

A change in rotation has also been observed in the cases of 2'- and 4'-dimethylaminocamphoranilic acids (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 745). The 2'-dimethylamino acid has a slight positive rotation $[\alpha]_D = 6.2^\circ$ in the neutral medium which increased very little in the presence of alkali, but the rotatory power increased enormously $[\alpha]_D = 57.0^\circ$ when an equivalent amount of an acid was added. 4'-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic acid (*loc. cit.*) likewise shows similar behaviour with acids and alkalis. *p*-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 219) also resembles these substances in as much as its rotatory power varies considerably when it is converted into its methiodide,

The present paper extends these investigations to the cases of camphoranilic and a few substituted camphoranilic acids as well as to α - and β -naphthylcamphoramidic acids both in the pure state as well as in various stages of neutralisation with different alkalis.

Camphoranilic Acid.

The following table contains the rotatory powers of camphoranilic acid at various degrees of neutralisation with LiOH, NaOH and KOH.

TABLE I.

Solutions of camphoranilic acid (0.2750 g./25 c.c.) and increasing amounts of alkali (x_m).

x_m .	[α] ₀ .			x_m .	[α] ₀ .		
	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.		LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.
0.00	48.2°	48.2°	48.2°	0.50	69.0°	65.0°	65.4°
0.125	52.7	50.0	51.8	0.625	56.8	59.5	56.8
0.250	54.5	51.8	53.0	0.750	60.0	62.2	60.0
0.375	57.7	54.5	57.8	0.875	66.3	64.5	63.2
				1.00	67.7	67.2	68.2

A series of camphoranilic acid solutions were prepared by the addition of the smallest amount of alcohol (2.3 c.c.) and then the required amount of alkali so that solutions with increasing degree of neutralisation were obtained. It will be found that in every case there is a gradual rise till the half neutralisation point. There is then a sudden fall and then a continued rise till the acid is completely neutralised. The result is shown by a typical curve in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Camphoranilic acid (LiOH).

An abrupt change at half neutralisation points to a probability of the formation of a new compound, possibly an acid salt, all attempts at isolation of which have, however, been unsuccessful. It is quite likely that there is a loose combination which breaks up when crystallisation is attempted.

β -Naphthylcamphoramic Acid.

This resembles camphoranilic acid very closely in its behaviour. The following table records the values with increasing amounts of LiOH, NaOH, and KOH. In every case there is a steady rise in the rotatory power till the half neutralisation point and then a sudden fall followed by a gradual rise. Here also the values with the exception of that at the half neutralisation point, obey the additive law.

TABLE II.

x_m .	[α] _b .			x_m .	[α] _b .		
	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.		LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.
0'00	69'0*	69'0*	69'0*	0'625	77'5*	80'0*	79'5*
0'125	71'0	76'0	72'0	0'750	83'0	83'5	82'0
0'250	74'5	79'0	76'0	0'875	90'0	86'5	85'0
0'375	77'5	81'0	79'5	1'00	95'0	91'0	88'5
0'500	82'5	86'0	84'0				

Changes are all similar and have been typically represented in Fig. 2.

Substituted Camphoranilic Acids.

2'-3'- & 4'-Methylcamphoranilic acids show a different behaviour from those mentioned above. The following table contains the rotatory powers of these acids with increasing amounts of alkali (x_m).

TABLE III.

2'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.				4'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.		
x_m .	[α] _b .			[α] _b .		
	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.
0'00	48'0*	—	48'0*	57'4	57'4	57'4
0'125	51'0	—	50'0	59'2	62'3	59'2
0'250	55'0	—	52'5	59'2	62'3	59'2
0'375	58'0	—	55'0	59'2	63'2	59'6
0'500	57'5	—	54'5	59'2	63'2	59'6
0'625	57'5	—	55'0	59'6	63'6	59'2
0'750	60'0	—	57'5	60'1	68'2	63'2
0'875	63'0	—	60'5	64'0	70'0	66'6
1'00	67'0	—	65'0	68'7	—	70'0
				70'0	76'1	73'5

3'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.

x_m .	[α] _b .		
	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.
0'00	49'0	49'0	49'0
0'125	50'0	50'0	50'0
0'250	52'5	54'5	52'5
0'375	57'5	58'0	57'5
0'500	57'0	58'0	57'0
0'625	58'0	58'0	58'0
0'750	60'0	—	60'0
0'875	—	62'5	—
1'00	67'0	68'5	67'0

In all these cases the rotatory powers increase and then become constant till 0.625 of the acid is neutralised, and increase again till the acid is completely neutralised.

α-Naphthylcamphoramic acid behaves like methylcamphoranilic acids. But in this, as already pointed out, the rotatory power of the alkali salts is twice as much as that of the free acid.

TABLE IV.

α_m .	[α] _D			α_m .	[α] _D		
	LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.		LiOH.	NaOH.	KOH.
0.00	20.0	20.0	20.0	0.50	31.5	28.5	29.5
0.125	23.5	—	27.0	0.625	31.5	28.0	28.5
0.250	27.0	23.0	—	0.750	36.0	30.5	—
0.375	31.0	27.0	28.5	0.875	39.5	35.5	44.0
				1.00	42.5	40.0	50.5

It is now proposed to study the effect of electrolytes like LiCl, NaCl and KCl etc. on the rotatory powers of the alkali salts and determine some physical constants.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with Different Amines.

The method was that described for the condensation of chloroanilines (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1995).

The alternative method of heating camphoric anhydride with the amine in chloroform was also used. The chloroform solution is heated for 8-9 hours on the water-bath. Excess of chloroform is removed and the solid mass is crystallised from alcohol.

Camphoranilic acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as a crystalline powder, m.p. 201.5-202.5°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents.

2'-Methylcamphoranilic acid crystallised into white crystalline mass. m.p. 193.5-94.5°.

3'- & 4'-Methylcamphoranilic acid, melt respectively at m.p. 209-209° and 212.5-214.5°.

α-Naphthylcamphoramic acid, m.p. 231.5-232.5° and *β-naphthylcamphoramic acid*, m.p. 212-214° had to be crystallised (animal charcoal) a number of times to free them of the colouring matter.

The rotatory powers of these acids were determined by dissolving a known weight of the acid in 2-3 c.c. of alcohol and then adding a known volume of standard alkali. The remaining volume was made up by adding distilled water.